

THE MAIN FEATURES OF THE FINNISH MIRACLE IN EDUCATION AND ITS APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN

Bekmamadova Gulnoza Akmalovna

Associate Professor of the Tashkent University of Architecture and Civil Engineering,
e-mail - g.bekmamadova@yahoo.com

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***Abstract.** Education in Finland ranks one of the first places in authoritative world rankings. Thus, students of general education schools constantly show a high level of reading and science literacy, and high knowledge in mathematics. Finnish higher education is popular throughout the world and attracts students from a wide variety of countries. This article is devoted to the analysis of the features and factors that determine the success of education in Finland. This article examines the stages of education and the structural characteristics of the education system in Finland, considers a number of its specific features, and classifies efficiency factors. Also, the issue of comparing the education systems of Finland and Uzbekistan is separately considered.*

***Keywords:** destratification, water catchment area, hydrochemical and hydrobiological conditions, eutrophication of water bodies.*

***Аннотация.** Образование Финляндии занимает одно из первых мест в авторитетных мировых рейтингах. Так, обучающиеся общеобразовательной школы постоянно показывают высокий уровень читательской и естественнонаучной грамотности, высокие познания в математике. Финское высшее образование является популярным во всем мире и привлекает студентов из самых различных стран. Данная статья посвящена анализу особенностей и факторов, обуславливающих успешность образования в Финляндии. В данной статье изучены этапы образования и на структурных характеристиках системы образования в Финляндии, рассматривают ряд её специфических особенностей, классифицируют факторы эффективности. Также, отдельно рассмотрен вопрос сравнения систем образования Финляндии и Узбекистана.*

***Ключевые слова:** Finnish miracle, education system, student-centered pedagogy, preschool education, basic general education, preparatory education, second-level education.*

1. Introduction.

Recently, large-scale reforms in the field of education have been carried out in Uzbekistan. In this regard, from high stands they began to talk a lot about the Finnish experience in education. Thus, during a visit to the Syrdarya region, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev announced the creation of textbooks for primary schools according to the “Finnish standard”, since “public education in Finland is competitive in Europe and throughout the world”. Later, during a meeting with the president on the development of the Kashkadarya region, it was instructed to introduce the Finnish education system in 48 schools in the region, starting from the next school year.

Each state has its own unique system of education, on which its progressive development, forward movement, and social well-being largely depend. The peculiarities of education in Finland, a small country with a population of a little more than five million people, have repeatedly become the subject of pedagogical research (G.R. Islakaeva, M.B. Ponyavina, I.S. Pozdeeva, E.E. Sin, M.F. Solovyova, M.V. Yushkova, K. Huusko, etc.). The reason for the close attention to the organization of the educational process in the country lies in the high learning outcomes at various levels, the universal recognition of the effectiveness of education. It is known that Finland's

education system is one of the most effective in the modern world, and ensuring its high level is a priority of the country's national strategy.

The “Finnish miracle in education” was discussed after the announcement of the results of the first International Program for the Assessment of Educational Achievements of Students (PISA) in 2000. [1] Finland ranked first among 32 countries participating in the study with 546 points in reading literacy (the average score was 500), fifth in mathematical literacy with 536 points (after Hong Kong, Japan, South Korea and New Zealand) and fourth in natural science literacy with 538 points (after South Korea, Japan and Hong Kong).

Education in Finland is based on the principles of personality-oriented pedagogy, which include: educational partnership, equality, dialogue, taking into account the individual characteristics of each student. In addition, a distinctive feature of the education system is its practical orientation (learning for life, not for exams). For the reasons outlined above, the study of Finnish education is possible in order to introduce the positive experience of this country into the domestic educational space in the conditions of its reform.

2. The educational system of Finland

Finland has a high level of education. The difference in results between schools is insignificant, and almost all students graduate from school on time. Preparatory education, secondary education and second-level education are free, and subsequent education is also free in most cases. It is assumed that everyone, regardless of the level of family income, should have equal opportunities to get a quality education and become an active citizen of the country.

The education system includes preschool education, preparatory education, secondary education, second-level education and higher education. Special education is provided for adults. Within the framework of adult education, there are many training options, from mastering the secondary school program to higher education.

2.1. Preschool education

In Finland, every child who has not reached school age has the right to preschool education (varhaiskasvatus). Preschool education is carried out in municipal and family kindergartens. The child can also participate in outdoor activities for preschoolers together with one of the parents, for example, on playgrounds. The goal is to promote the development and well-being of the child and to ensure equality in learning. In the process of preschool education, social and language skills are formed, fine motor skills are developed and other skills and knowledge are acquired. Also, the child learns skills that will help him in his further studies. [2]

During the day, children play and walk a lot. If the child's native language is not Finnish or Swedish, he is provided with assistance in learning Finnish or Swedish. Children with special needs can also receive correctional assistance.

2.2. Preparatory training

In accordance with Finnish legislation, before starting school, children must undergo preparatory training (esiopetus) for one year. Usually, preparatory training begins when the child turns six years old. The municipalities are engaged in the organization of preparatory training, and it is free for the family. Specialists in the field of preschool education with higher pedagogical education work with children. Usually a child is engaged in preschool from Monday to Friday for four hours a day, during school hours. Simultaneously with the preparatory education, the child can receive preschool education.

During the year, the child learns the skills that he will need at school, for example, the alphabet. However, children are not learning to read at this stage yet. If the child's native language is not Finnish or Swedish, he is provided with assistance in learning Finnish or Swedish. During the day, children also play and walk a lot.[3]

2.3. Basic general education

Basic general education (perusopetus) in Finland begins in the year when a child turns seven years old. All children permanently residing in Finland are required to receive basic general education. Secondary school education lasts nine years.

In Finland, basic general education is regulated by law. Additionally, there is a state basic curriculum, as well as local curricula.

Municipalities organize basic general education, and it is free for families. The school year lasts 38 weeks, lessons are 45 minutes each. Children study languages, mathematics, natural sciences and health sciences, religion and ethics, history and social studies, art, home economics and physical education, as well as elective subjects. In addition, special hours are allocated for consultations on functional and metacognitive skills (the ability to control your learning process) and choosing a profession. The weekly load on a student is low compared to other European countries: in the 1st and 2nd grades, the minimum load is 20 hours and increases to 27 hours in high school (for comparison: in Uzbekistan - from 22 to 34 hours per week). The atmosphere in schools is relaxing, there are no clothing requirements, textbooks and lunch are provided free of charge, and long breaks between lessons allow you to play and relax. [4]

In Finland, all secondary school teachers have a master's degree. Teachers of grades 1-6 have a general pedagogical education. And the teachers of grades 7-9 have an education with specialization in the subjects they teach.

In matters of planning the educational process, teachers have more freedom and independently plan classes based on national and local curricula. Recently, special attention has been paid in the curriculum, in particular, to blocks that include several subjects, the study of everyday phenomena, as well as information and communication technologies.

Often, from 1st to 6th grade, the same teacher works with children. He gets to know the students well and therefore can build training in accordance with their level and characteristics. An important feature of the educational process is teaching independent thinking and fostering a responsible attitude to learning.

The teacher evaluates the progress of the students. In high school, all grades are given by the teacher. National tests are not conducted in high school. Instead, student achievement is monitored through selective assessment. Assessment activities are usually conducted in the ninth grade.

If a child or teenager has recently moved to Finland, he can take training that will prepare him for high school. Usually the preparatory training lasts one year. If after that the student still needs help in mastering the language, he will be able to continue studying Finnish or Swedish as a second language (S2-kieli).

2.4. Second stage education

The most common options for education after graduation are gymnasium (lukio) and secondary vocational education (ammattillinen koulutus). They belong to the second stage of education. Second-level education is free for students.

In 2021, the content of the concept of compulsory education in Finland was expanded. After secondary school, all students must continue their studies until the end of the second stage or the age of 18.

A teenager must apply for admission to a second-level institution if he is a student of the 9th grade of a primary school in the spring of 2021 or later.

Gymnasium

It is necessary to apply for admission to the gymnasium within the framework of the nationwide enrollment of students in second-level educational institutions in February-March. You can enter the gymnasium if you have completed the basic school program or the program corresponding to the basic school program. Gymnasiums, as a rule, select students on the basis of a certificate of completion of primary school. Gymnasiums can also take into account other education and hobbies of the applicant. In some gymnasiums, an entrance exam is held, according to the results of which a part of the points is formed.

Education at the gymnasium is of a general educational nature and does not involve obtaining any specialty. The gymnasium studies mostly the same subjects as in secondary school, but at a more complex level. In addition, studying requires more independence. Studying at the gymnasium ends with passing the exam for admission to a higher educational institution. Education in the gymnasium lasts from 2 to 4 years, depending on the capabilities and desires of the student. After that, you can enter a university, a university of applied sciences or an educational institution offering secondary vocational education on the basis of a gymnasium. [5]

Education in most gymnasiums is conducted in Finnish or Swedish. There are also several gymnasiums in large cities, where education is conducted in a foreign language, for example, in English or French.

Adults can study courses from the gymnasium program in gymnasiums for adults. In them, you can study both individual courses and the entire gymnasium program, as well as pass an exam for admission to a higher educational institution. Training may include lectures and classes at an educational institution, distance learning, webinars and independent work.

Secondary vocational education

It can be applied for secondary vocational training as part of the current enrollment of students year-round or as part of a nationwide enrollment in second-level educational institutions. Nationwide recruitment is usually held in February-March. The order of enrollment of students depends on the educational institution. Usually, entrance scores are taken into account when recruiting, which depend, among other things, on the grades in your certificate. Many educational institutions also conduct entrance exams or aptitude tests.

Secondary vocational education is more practice-oriented than gymnasium education. It gives the opportunity to get a qualification in a certain profession in about three years. Employed persons can also receive additional professional or specialized vocational education. On-the-job training is an essential part of vocational education. If desired, after receiving secondary vocational education, you can enroll in a higher educational institution.

It is also possible to obtain a diploma of vocational education or specialized vocational education on the basis of passing a demonstration exam. To do this, you must already possess the knowledge and skills necessary to obtain the appropriate diploma.

Diploma of professional education can also be get a as a result of training under a contract. In this case, the student works in the specialty, receives a salary for his work equal to at least the amount of payment for the passage of labor practice, and at the same time learns the profession.

A good knowledge of the language is necessary for the second stage of education. If the student's native language is not Finnish or Swedish, and the level of knowledge of these languages is insufficient for studying at a gymnasium or a vocational educational institution, preparatory training for TUVVA diploma programs can be completed before admission.

2.5. Higher education

After graduating from the first-level educational institution, person can continue his studies at a higher educational institution. In Finland, higher education can be obtained at universities of applied sciences and universities. Higher education institutions and educational institutions independently decide on the enrollment of students.

Education at a higher educational institution can be either free or paid. For citizens of non-EU countries, as well as for their family members who study at English-language bachelor's or master's degree programs, education is paid. [6]

Universities of Applied Sciences

Studying at the University of Applied Sciences is closer to practice than studying at the university. The training also includes an industrial practice. The duration of training is from 3.5 to 4.5 years. If after that person wish to continue your studies and get a master's degree from the University of Applied Sciences, he will need to acquire two years of work experience in the specialty.

Documents for the diploma program to the University of Applied Sciences are submitted if one of the following requirements is met:

- the gymnasium program has been completed;
- a unified state exam has been passed, giving the right to enter the university\$
- there is a diploma of professional qualification;
- there is a bachelor's or master's degree.

Documents for admission to the University of Applied Sciences should be submitted as part of a nationwide recruitment process. The nationwide recruitment is held three times a year: twice in spring and once in autumn.

Most students are admitted to universities of applied sciences on the basis of a certificate of completion of basic school or grades contained in a diploma of basic vocational education. The remaining students are selected through a single entrance exam. If person has passed the selection on the basis of certification certificates, then it is not need to take a single entrance exam.

There is an opportunity to enroll in the Master's program of the University of Applied Sciences if you have a diploma of the University of Applied Sciences or other relevant higher education and work experience in the field corresponding to the education received for at least two years, while work experience was obtained after graduation.

It can be applied for the master's program of a higher professional educational institution within the framework of a nationwide recruitment in spring or autumn.

Universities

Education at the university is of a research nature. At university, you can get a bachelor's degree in about three years, and then a master's degree in about two years. Universities organize training in English in some areas. However, most of the programs are taught in Finnish or Swedish.

Documents for admission to the university are submitted as part of the nationwide recruitment to universities (held in spring and autumn) or as part of a specialized recruitment conducted directly by the university. [7]

Most students are admitted to the university on the basis of a certificate of completion of primary school. The remaining students are selected on the basis of an entrance exam, or other selection methods may be used.

3. Features of the Finnish education system: comparison with Uzbekistan

Let's consider the key features of the Finnish education system in comparison with the Uzbek one. It must be remembered that the functioning of any education system depends on many factors: historical, economic, social, cultural and others.

The World Bank experts note the following features of Finnish society that radically distinguish it from many other countries and leave their mark, including on the education system: a small, ethnically and culturally homogeneous (homogeneous) population (only 4% of the population is not of Finnish origin) and a high level of per capita income. The population of Uzbekistan is not only numerous, but also diverse in ethnic, cultural and religious terms.

Exploring the historical and sociological roots of the "Finnish miracle", Hannu Simola from the University of Helsinki notes that in Finland the transition from an agrarian to an industrial and further post-industrial society occurred very quickly, and the same accelerated progress can be traced in the field of education: the system of universal education began to be introduced only in the 1970s and implemented it “quickly, systematically and even in a totalitarian way”.

Simola writes that one of the key features of the reforms in the country's education system in the 1970s was the rejection of the division of schools into “strong” and “ordinary” and the introduction of the same comprehensive schools for all. The World Bank also notes that the rejection of early separation of children (according to abilities and interests) is one of the key features of Finnish school education.

In Uzbekistan, experts say, the strategy for the development of education and science provides for the creation of separate schools for gifted children, such as, for example, presidential and specialized schools, which are accepted from the fifth or seventh grade.

Secondary schools are the same not only in terms of the program, but also in terms of funding. Part of the funding comes from the central budget and part from the local budget. Schools receive the same funding and the amount of funding is tied to the number of students. [8]

Another important aspect of the reforms in the Finnish education system in the 1970s was the shift of primary school teacher training from colleges and seminaries to the newly created faculties of education at universities, as well as the introduction of the Master's level requirement for teachers. Now, in order to teach in elementary school, you need to have a master's degree in education, and in secondary school — a master's degree in the discipline taught. For comparison: 13% of teachers in Uzbekistan have specialized secondary or incomplete higher education.

As a rule, teaching faculties in Finland have at least 60 credits out of 300 required for obtaining a master's degree (180 credits in bachelor's degree and 120 in master's degree) they are allocated to subjects related to pedagogy, and from 15% to a third of the study time is devoted to pedagogical practice. Professional development of existing teachers is the responsibility of local municipalities, and since they decide how to spend the budget, the opportunities and forms of professional development may vary depending on the region and school.

In Uzbekistan, as a rule, the system of professional development is regulated by government regulations and is the same for everyone. Only recently, teachers were given the right to choose an educational institution for advanced training.

According to research, the competition for pedagogical directions in Finland is one of the highest. For example, in recent years, on average, about 7000 applicants have applied for 900 places in primary school teacher training faculties. Despite relatively low salaries compared to other fields (for example, an elementary school teacher receives 22% less than other specialists with a master's degree, and a first—level secondary school teacher receives 15% less) and increasing stress levels, many teachers feel satisfied and committed to their work: only 10-15% of teachers change the field activities for the whole career. There is also a high level of trust and respect for teachers on the part of parents.

Another turning point in Finland's education reforms, according to Hannu Simola, was the rejection of formal control over teachers and schools in the 1990s: “all traditional control mechanisms, such as inspection of schools, detailed curricula, official approval of textbooks and teaching materials, journals where teachers had to record every lesson "they all disappeared”.

Pasi Salberg, an education expert, author of the book "Finnish Lessons", dedicated to the reforms of Finland in the field of education, writes that in Finland teachers are given greater autonomy. Teachers should evaluate their students and provide reports on their progress, but they can develop their own programs that they think will best suit students. The World Bank notes that the system is based on mutual trust: the Finnish Center for Education Assessment (FINEEC) conducts regular assessment in a sample of schools, but does not compare schools with each other, and those schools where such assessment is not carried out use their assessment methods to diagnose and correct learning problems.

In general, many researchers note decentralization and the granting of autonomy to municipalities and schools as one of the important results of reforms in the Finnish education system. For example, the national curriculum defines goals and objectives for each of the school subjects, as well as general provisions regarding the educational environment, training and assessment, but municipalities and schools draw up their own programs based on the national curriculum and taking into account local specifics and the needs of their students.[9]

In Uzbekistan, secondary schools must strictly follow the programs and plans approved by the Ministry of Public Education. The State Inspectorate for Supervision of the Quality of Education accredits schools and makes their rating, and teachers must undergo regular certification, the procedure of which is regulated by a decree of the Cabinet of Ministers.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be noted that the reason for the success of Finnish education is decentralization, teacher training and the availability of the same education for all. Education in Finland is based on a personality-oriented approach and comfortable conditions have been created for all participants in the process.

However, despite the success of the reforms of the Finnish educational system is often used as a model of successful reforms in education, the ideas and principles applied in Finland since the 1970s will not necessarily work in other cultural or social contexts.

Indeed, the education system is a complex mechanism consisting of many interdependent elements, such as, for example, educational standards and curricula, educational institutions, an assessment system, specialists working in the system, their training and retraining, and copying

one or more links in the chain without taking into account their interaction with other elements may not bear fruit.

In this regard, it is necessary to incorporate the best of the Finnish education system into the educational system of Uzbekistan (unloading teachers from unnecessary reports, providing independence in drawing up curricula, etc.).

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